

Comparison of Students' Perceptions Concerning their Teachers Classroom Management Skills at Secondary Level

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to investigate “the comparison of students’ perceptions concerning their teachers’ classroom management skills at secondary level. From each school five teachers was selected as a sample or respondents; in these way 280 teachers were selected as a sample of the study. The sample of the study was finalized by using John Curry formula. For analysis Mean, Standard deviation and t-test were used. This insignificant dissimilarity amid the views of male and female learners reflects that both male and female teachers properly manage their classroom management skills. Analysis presented no noteworthy dissimilarity amid the opinions of urban and rural students regarding their teachers’ class room management skills. This insignificant dissimilarity amid the opinions of urban and rural learners reflects that teachers accurately accomplish teachers’ class room management skills.

Key Words: Management Skills, Schools, Classroom, Academic Achievement.

Introduction

Generally, no one can disregard the fact that teachers’ classroom management skills play a very important role to achieve students’ academic achievement at secondary level. Classroom management skills are necessary for teachers and students. The use of effective teacher classroom management skills increases student academic achievement at secondary level. As [Kellerman \(1998\)](#) indicates that strong relationship exists between the teachers’ classroom management skills and students’ academic achievement at secondary level.

It is a societal expectation that academic achievement is the result of the provision of education in schools, therefore society always looks for good schools and policy dictates what a good school is. The effectiveness of individual schools is analogous to the effectiveness of the education system in a country. School effectiveness ultimately translates into students’ achievement. Therefore, this study is concerned with the teachers’ classroom management skills and students’ academic achievement. The central theme of this thesis is the relationship between teachers’ classroom management skills and students’ academic achievement.

The purpose of this study was to find comparison of students’ perceptions concerning their teachers classroom management skills at secondary level Teachers’ classroom management skills include time management and effective communication, Seating arrangement and organizing instructional materials, maintaining student learning and inspiring their motivation, administration of student assignments and their academic works, using consequences and expectations of students’ behaviors, creating a learning environment and improving group decision making. On the other hand as Dee cited in McMillan & Schumacher (2010) it originates teachers’ understanding along with major predictors of learner’ educational accomplishment. Though teachers’ teaching experiences as well as a learning skill considerably connected towards learner attainment.

This article focuses on a comparison of students’ perceptions concerning their teachers’ classroom management skills at secondary level that provides a structure at a practical and operational level from

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which teachers can operate to work together to address their common needs and achieve their goals. The comparison of students' perceptions concerning their teachers' classroom management skills is not a new concept, but more and more organisations in the education profession in various countries are currently underwriting this concept owing to the abundant research supporting comparison of students' perceptions concerning their teachers' classroom management skills, and the fact that organisations, created for the specific purpose of making the education profession more rewarding, satisfying and effective.

The findings and conclusions of this research study have great scope for the development of the learners. The researchers not only focus on the Pakistani but also for the whole world. Therefore, the findings and conclusion of the present research study also applicable for all over the teaching and learning process. The management skills are those skills which enable the teachers to developed all those capacities in the learner which capable to fulfill all the needs and demands of the nation. The researcher fully concentration on that area to achieve the maximum learning outcomes.

Secondary schooling must be perceived as a total stage in itself and sorted out as a different scholastic and regulatory unit. It might incorporate that part of the improvement of the kid as a person, as a resident, as a specialist and as a loyalist to empower him to appreciate and comprehend the advantages of social, monetary and moral advancement Dai, Swanson and Cheng (2011).

Modern trends in learning highlight the significance of the curriculum, course outline, content, instruction methods, direction, counseling, audio-visual aids, inspiration, willingness, amenities, etc., however teacher's have need classroom management skills for the implementation of such methods and technique in the teaching learning process. Although it is also more necessary that teachers have some desirable and attractive stage of mastery of teachers' classroom management skills of subject matter. If teachers desire to get better and to gather the rising requirements of expectations production than it is essential to raise the superiority of normal of teachers' room management skills. It requires ability in preparation with expertise in the classroom teaching.

There are confident particular ability to construct single instructor additional effectual than anymore, during the radiance of this declaration several announce to effectual teachers are naturally with the talent to instruct further mocking at this concept as well as assert that it is likely to expand and teach someone to be a successful teacher. Secondary education is an essential and middle sub-sector of the entire education organization in the state. On the other hand secondary schooling provides center stage human resources for the nation as well as on the other hand secondary schooling provides appropriate contribution for the advanced level of learning. In instruction erudition procedure superiority of advanced teaching which is required for the expansion of the nation and create high excellence professionals in life.

Education is an extremely basic human action. It helps any general public means and model people to work well with their condition. According to Abdullah, 2011 the motivation behind training is to prepare the citizenry to reshape their general public and dispense with disparity. Specifically, optional instruction is an essential segment in national and individual advancement. It assumes an indispensable part in making a nation's human asset base at more elevated amount than essential training [Aaronson, Barrow and Sander, 2007](#). The key pretended by auxiliary instruction may incompletely disclose the administration's choice to present free educating out in the open optional schools so as to build its request [McCaslin and Good, 1998](#).

Objectives of the Study

1. To know the perceptions of students concerning their teacher's classroom organization skills at secondary level.
2. To compare the perceptions of students by gender and locality concerning their teacher's classroom organization skills at secondary level.

Research Hypotheses

- Ho1. There is no significant dissimilarity between the perceptions of students' concerning their teachers' classroom organization skills.
- Ho2. There is no significant dissimilarity among the perceptions of students by gender concerning their teachers' classroom organization skills.
- Ho3. There is no significant difference among the perceptions of students by locality regarding their teachers' classroom management skills.

Literature Review

[Brophy \(1988\)](#) study in Ghana found that factors which considerably contribute to lack of educational accomplishment was due to the incidence of unpunctuality in school, incidence of absence, as well as presentation, particularly while well explanation, motivation, corrected and reviewed through class occasion along with used an instance in response to the learner capability to entire syllabi. Liston and Zeichner (2013) fulfilled organization skills of homework along with training include students' educational accomplishment.

The idea of time has been discussed in the past, and it has been articulated in dissimilar ways that time is of vital importance for all beings in the universe. Although, time is the same for everybody, actually, time cannot be borrowed or lent; time cannot be saved or changed and it can only be used. Having this along with similar other features, time is vital for individuals and organizations. In view of the literature, it is clear that the concept of time has been defined as an abstract and important value in which events flow spontaneously, and which all beings in the universe own equally Barbetta, Noronaand Bicard (2005).

The concept of time management appeared in Denmark as an educational tool to help better organization of time, and spread to all over the world from there. Nowadays, however, it has become one of the most important elements of personal and corporate success, especially in the professional work life. Some authors have also likened it to human life, and argued that managing time is actually managing life. Besides, time is unmanageable in reality; however, individuals can manage activities in their lives. In descriptions made on time management, the opinion that efficient use of time is necessary for an individual or organization has gained importance [Edwards, J. R. \(2008\)](#).

Effective instruction also enables the teacher to be release bright thoughts as well as build up helpful instruction attitudes [Gibson and Dembo \(1984\)](#); [Tschannen-Moran and Hoy \(2001\)](#) with obtaining additional accountability in schooling. Exploring the connection between effective instruction and occupation agreement might include implications for teachers' work presentation, with addition, the educational attainment of learner. It might too declare to present exists a positive connection, connecting effective instruction, faith connected to schooling and position [Coladarci \(1992\)](#).

Motivation is a theoretical construct used to explain the initiation, direction, intensity, and persistence of goal-oriented behavior, Good and [Brophy \(1995\)](#). There are many theories and views surrounding motivation, and no single method is going to be effective one hundred percent of the time. The better a teacher can do is to have a balanced knowledge of these views, and be able to adapt with different groups and individual students as best as possible. Many of the theories of motivation encompass similar concepts. Generally, there are two types of motivation, one that is driven by personal satisfaction of mastering the material and the other by the reward or benefit those results [Lepper and Hodell \(2016\)](#) cited two kinds of motivation: extrinsic and intrinsic.

Extrinsic motivation is caused by outside factors, such as a reward, whereas intrinsic motivation stems since the student's own wish to study and master the material. This is similar to Task vs. Ego involvement, where a task involved student has a genuine interest in the material and an ego-centered student learns it for the pure benefit of passing an exam or being able to "show-off" that knowledge [Duda and Nicholls \(1992\)](#).

According to Good and Brophy (1995) intrinsic motivational strategies should increase student's enjoyment of classroom activities; they will not increase the student's motivation to learn the content or skills being taught. Another factor in motivation seems to involve a student's self-concept, or what they

perceive as the reasons for their success or failure. Covington’s analysis of motivation encompasses similar ideas, but in this case placement of blame is used more as a “tool” to avoid feeling like a failure. Therefore, on one hand the student may study hard and do well, but primarily out of fear they will fail. On the other hand, they may not study at all, but they won’t count the failure as their own since they actively chose not to put forth the effort. The logic is that it’s better to not study at all than to study and still fail [Covington and Omelich \(1984\)](#). It is important for students to see that what they put in; through their own effort they have control over their learning.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual frame discusses the dimensions of the present research study which explore the teachers’ classroom management skills such as Time Management and effective communication of teacher, Seating arrangement and organizing instructional materials, maintain students’ learning, and inspiring their motivation, administration of students’ assignments and their academic work, using consequences, and expectation of students’ behavior, creating learning environment and improving group decision making.

This conceptual framework provides the base for understanding teachers’ classroom management skills and their relation to students’ academic achievement at secondary school level. On the basis of the conceptual frame work, this study also provides to identify to what extent teachers’ classroom management skills affect students’ academic achievement.

Figure 1: Theoretical/ Conceptual Framework of the Study

Research Methodology

Population of the Study

Population of the study was comprised of all the students of Government secondary schools in southern districts (Dera ismail khan, Tank, Bannu, Lakki, Kohat, Hongu and Karak) of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

Sample of the Study

Table 1. The Description of Sample

Sample Districts	Male School	Female School	Male students	Female students
Bannu	04	04	15	15
Lakki	04	04	15	15
D.I.Khan	04	04	15	15
Karak	04	04	15	15
Kohat	04	04	15	15
Tank	04	04	15	15
Hongu	04	04	15	15
Total	28	28	420	420
	56		840	

Sample of the study consisted of 840 learners similarly the whole métier of the sample were 840 defendants. The Southern districts comprised of Kohat, Houngu, Tank, Karark, Bannu, Lakki and Dera ismail Khan. Then the researcher arbitrarily elected 8 schools from every district. The investigator completed strata of the sample male and female schools by using stratified accidental sampling method. The researcher then used sample random sampling method for collection of learners as respondents of the study from the elected schools. The researcher randomly nominated 15 students from every school. In this way from the total district elected respondents were 840 students (see table 1). Curry, R. A., et al (2013) explain sample range Rule of Thumb as under

Population range	Sample Size
101-1,000	10%
1,001-5,000	5%
5,001-10,000	3%
10,000+	1%

[Francis, A., et al \(2004\)](#) declared to “here is not specific respond used for precise sample variety; it depends upon the reason of the learning and the nature of the inhabitants beneath inspection”.

Mode of Data Collection

Researcher personally visited sampled schools and distributed the questionnaire amongst learners. The investigator required approval from school heads for collection of data from respondents. The process of collection of data was properly organized and respondents take the responsibility and filled questionnaire was returned on time.

Data Analysis Techniques

The composed information was entered in “SPSS- 23” applied for treatment. Similarly, the scenery of the objectives of the learning descriptive statistical technique used. To evaluate perceptions by sexual category and region concerning teachers’ classroom organization skills Mean, Standard Deviation and t. test of independent were used

Results and Discussions

Table 2. Showing Item Wise Mean and Standard Deviation of Teacher Classroom Management Skills at the Secondary Level

S.No	Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	You manage due time for each activity in the classroom.	840	4.4714	.61110

2	You regularly schedule time for each working day.	840	4.2857	.67249
3	You do time management planning for students' learning.	840	4.2155	.75795
4	You care about the students' time on priority basis.	840	4.1357	.67169
5	You effectively communicate assignments with students.	840	4.0952	.79957
6	Your communication regarding your academic work is clear and understandable.	840	4.2333	.61202
7	You communicate feedback effectively to students.	840	4.2321	.64563
8	You explain key points to ensure understanding of the students.	840	4.3262	.59859
9	You make an effort to improve students' behavior in the classroom.	840	4.4286	.65660
10	You ensure good behavior feedback in the classroom.	840	4.1988	.70904
11	You appreciate good behavior of students in the classroom.	840	4.2107	.81091
12	You set good expectations of students' behaviors in the classroom.	840	4.1738	.70468
13	You convey the consequences of bad behavior to students.	840	4.1429	.80734
14	You respect the students' positive opinions in the classroom.	840	4.1714	.85080
15	You make sure that students in his/her classroom follow the rules and regulation all the time.	840	4.0298	1.01259
16	You ensure a pleasant learning environment for all the students.	840	4.1690	.83144
17	You motivate students to maintain discipline.	840	4.2774	.75981
18	You ensure equal participation of all students in learning activities.	840	4.1762	.80369
19	You make conducive learning environment in the classroom.	840	4.1619	.73559
20	You give adequate space to the suggestions of students in decision making.	840	4.1036	.83999
21	You incorporate the students' views in decision making.	840	4.1298	.79394
22	You make positive decisions in classroom activities.	840	4.1786	.73172
23	You make motivational decisions about classroom learning activities.	840	4.0940	.87310
24	You make proper seating arrangements in the classroom.	840	4.0869	.91123
25	Your skills of seating arrangement do teaching, learning attractive and interesting.	840	3.9083	1.01123
26	You clearly explain key points with the help of A.V aids.	840	4.1262	.90990
27	You ensure proper use of instructional materials.	840	4.0631	.84400
28	You ensure participation of students in the use of relevant instructional materials.	840	4.1440	.85238
29	You organize instructional materials for student learning.	840	4.1048	.86156
30	You use other instructional sources rather than books in the classroom.	840	4.0702	.92047
31	You provide feedback to clarify students' assignment.	840	4.1476	.93641
32	You provide materials for the completion of students' assignment.	840	4.3976	.64329
33	You organize assignments well to increase students learning.	840	4.0976	.94168

34	You give homework to students to improve classroom outcomes.	840	4.2643	.81063
35	You present the academic work clear and interesting way.	840	4.2762	.79474
36	You give detail information on students' academic work.	840	4.0786	1.01174
37	You make good techniques for explaining students' academic work.	840	4.1536	.92327
38	You manage academic work to enhance students' outcomes.	840	4.0738	.82527
39	You show enthusiasm to maintain students' learning.	840	4.1095	.83710
40	You use black board to clarify students learning.	840	4.3464	.64974
41	You give positive comments on students' learning.	840	4.1738	.87382
42	Your effective communication maintains students the learning in the classroom.	840	4.1524	.94830
43	You interlink students' previous knowledge to new learning.	840	4.1881	.81133
44	You use charts to maintain students' motivation.	840	4.2155	.90291
45	You encourage students to maintain their motivation.	840	4.2750	.79740
46	You motivate the students to take active part in co-curricular activities.	840	4.3048	.74205

Note. Mean score of total items= 4.345; Categorization of mean (1) 0---2.49 = "Below Average" (2) 2.50---3.49 = "Average" (3) 3.50---5.00 = "above average"

Table 2 revealed that Mean scores on all the items of the scale fall in the above average Mean category (3.50—5.00), viewing that teacher's classroom organizational skills are up-to-the mark in all features.

Table 3. Comparisons Amid the Opinions of Learners by Gender Regarding Teachers' Classroom Management Skills

S. No	Respondents	N	Mean	Std	T	Df	p-value
1	Male	420	1.94	10.85	0.453	723.821	.754
2	Female	420	1.90	10.52			

Note. A result is significant if p-value is equivalent to or less than 0.05 levels.

Table 3 revealed no noteworthy dissimilarity amongst the opinions of male and female students regarding their teachers' classroom management skills. The Probability value = 0.754 > α = 0.05, reflected no significance dissimilarity amid the opinions of male and female learners concerning their teachers classroom management skills. Both male as well as female learners grip parallel feelings about their teachers' classroom organizational skills. This insignificance dissimilarity amid the views of male and female learners reflects that both male and female teachers properly manage their classroom management skills.

Table 4. Comparisons Amid the Opinions of Learners by Area Regarding their Teachers' Classroom Management Skills

S. No	Respondents	N	Mean	Std	T	Df	p-value
1	Urban	420	1.93	13.79	0.2628	37.161	.654
2	Rural	420	1.90	14.30			

Note. A result is significant if p-value is equivalent to or less than 0.05 levels.

Table 4 presented no noteworthy dissimilarity amid the opinions of urban and rural students regarding their teachers' class room management skills. The Probability -value = $0.654 > \alpha = 0.05$, revealed no momentous dissimilarity amongst the visions of urban and rural teachers class room organizational skills. Both urban and rural learners grip comparable opinions concerning their teachers' class room management skills. This insignificant dissimilarity amid the opinions of urban and rural learners reflects that teachers accurately accomplish teachers' class room management skills.

Findings

The findings of the study revealed that Mean scores on all the items of the scale fall in the above average Mean category (3.50—5.00), viewing that teachers classroom organizational skills are up-to-the mark in all features. The study revealed that no noteworthy dissimilarity amongst the opinions of male and female students regarding their teachers' classroom management skills. The Probability value = $0.754 > \alpha = 0.05$, reflected no significance dissimilarity amid the opinions of male and female learners concerning their teachers classroom management skills. Both male as well as female learners grip parallel feelings about their teachers' classroom organizational skills. This insignificant dissimilarity amid the views of male and female learners reflects that both male and female teachers properly manage their classroom management skills.

Analysis also presented that no noteworthy dissimilarity amid the opinions of urban and rural students regarding their teachers' class room management skills. The Probability -value = $0.654 > \alpha = 0.05$, revealed no momentous dissimilarity amongst the visions of urban and rural teachers class room organizational skills. Both urban and rural learners grip comparable opinions concerning their teachers' class room management skills. This insignificant dissimilarity amid the opinions of urban and rural learners reflects that teachers accurately accomplish teachers' class room management skills.

Conclusion

There are two main conclusions of the present research article. No significant differences were originating among male and female students views regarding teachers class room management skills by gender. No significant differences were originate between urban and rural students opinions regarding teachers time managing and announcement, prospects of learners conduct and their penalties, educational situation and group judgment building, seating planning and establishing instructional substantial, direction of learners' assignment and academic work, continue learners' education and encouraging their inspiration and teachers classroom management skills by locality.

Recommendations

Following recommendations were made based on the conclusions:

1. Teachers having various academic qualifications and teaching experiences are in the favor of the use of teachers' class room management skills. The present study recommends giving properly training of teacher's class management skills to the teachers. So that they able to use their class room management skills in the secondary level for the better performance of the learner.
2. The present study concludes that teacher's class room management skills play basic role in the enhancement of students' academic achievement in at secondary stage. Therefore the present study recommends that educational planer and curriculum developer give much emphasis for the efficient use of teacher's class room management skills in the teaching learning process in all stages for the overall development of child.
3. The present study recommends that the government take step for the proper training and use of teacher's classroom management skills in the all stages of teaching learning process. Therefore the teachers ensured all possible methods and technique for the functionally developed of the learner. These are need and demands of the modern society and the nation for the progressive world.

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